

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING OF EFL STUDENTS IN UZBEKISTAN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Bringing up the generation who is able to think critically and creatively is one of the main missions of our nation since it enables the youth to tackle problems with confidence, communicate their thoughts and ideas clearly. Enhancing critical thinking in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classrooms is considered an important factor as it impacts on learner`s ability to learn a language more rapidly and effectively. Moreover, it brings a lot of enjoyment into learning process resulting students to become more engaged into learning process.

The term critical thinking goes back to 2500 years ago to Socrates who established the significance of asking deep questions that penetrate into thinking before the acceptance of the ideas as a praiseworthy of assurance. Socrates set up the importance of proof seeking, close examination of reasoning and assumptions, analysis of basic concepts determining implications both what is said well and done well. This way of analysis is acknowledged as “ Socratic Questioning” and the best known as critical thinking teaching strategy. In the method of questioning, Socrates highlighted the importance of thinking for precision and logical consistency.(1997). Socratic teaching is not solely teaching itself. It does not involve PPT lectures, thorough lesson plans or mechanical learning. The students are not inactive receivers of knowledge. This type of examination encourages intellectual humility and an enthusiasm to admit unawareness, leading to greater learning and understanding. Furthermore, it furthers evidence-based decision-making and consideration of alternative viewpoints. Hence, the Socratic Method is an essential tool for anyone looking for to develop his critical thinking skills and take on in meaningful communication. Socrates transformed the way we think about education. His

questioning techniques promoted a critical approach to learning that continues to have an influence on educational systems.(2003)

In the extended seminar of The Cabinet of Ministers that was dedicated to the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan The president Shavkat Mirziyayev made one of the important speeches about Critical thinking. Accordingly, every citizen of Uzbekistan must acquire the skills of critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility. All the levels of Educational system must be specialized into upbringing the youth who is able to think critically in all obstacles of life as Mirziyayev mentioned in the Seminar several times. Developing this skill prevents our youth from becoming indifferent, unmotivated and unsophisticated which guarantees that country`s future is in safe hands as our dear President cited. Moreover , he adds that only the youth who is able to think critically can make sensible and fair judgments in any situations and can defend their point of view.

Indeed, in our fast developing world, the country needs the youth who is capable of rebuilding modern society and tackling the issues with coming up creative ideas. The changes that are happening in a Modern Education highly demands applying new approaches which meet these demands. The primary goal of developing critical thinking skills of EFL students is not only educating them, but also enhancing the intellectual ability, which will be highly necessary in their later life. That is, making reasonable decisions, working with different kinds of information, analyzing the situations from different angles can serve as bright examples for this (Shamsiyeva 2023).So teachers together with parents have high responsibility of communicating with the students more encouraging them to think critically. In accordance with it, several reforms have been initiated in recent years. A bright example of this is The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” introduced on October 8, 2019. In accordance with the Decree, there are huge gaps in the Higher Education system that is the students do not possess the necessary critical and analytical skills. The decree proposes providing Universities and Instiutes with more freedom to allow them to put forward more individualized

teaching approach enhance students` creative thinking and motivate learners to be engaged in practice-based education. Moreover, the Decree highlights the importance of designing higher education academic programs that are actually built up on job market demand and students` interests. (Mirvokhidova 2024)

Undeniably, the higher education system of Uzbekistan has been facing with several positive changes in the recent years. Foundation of international, non-governmental and private universities has given new opportunities in the sphere of education. Presently, there are 224 functioning higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan in total. (Mirvokhidova 2024). As a result, the field has been seeing reasonably fair contest among universities to propose excellent education. Particularly, teaching English at universities as a foreign language has witnessed notable changes. Communication based and learner centered approaches of methodologies replaced traditional ways of teaching that were based on memorizing grammar, drilling and repetition

Foreign educators and researchers J.Braus and d.Vund define the term critical thinking as a sensible way of thinking that is based what to rely on and what to do. As they cited it is highest point of intelligence that is thinking sensibly and logically. The technology of critical thinking appeared in the USA in the 1980s and came into Russia in 1990s. Therefore, critical thinking is not a talent, but it is set up skills and abilities that are developed throughout years. It dramatically widens person`s horizon. By thinking critically, a student realizes the very root of any social and environmental issue. Critical thinking enables a person to become successful, happy, and rich and well- respected. By thinking critically one is able analyze core root of the issue, and make judgments about possible consequences of it. A student is able to think critically can take advantage of the evidence wisely, express his opinion precisely, differentiate the fake information from true one, and keep patient if there is not enough evidence to make a decision. (Soros 2004)

In conclusion, by thinking critically students are able to control and regulate the balance between their inner thoughts and the world. Therefore, it needs improving among language learners owing to its importance in developing efficient language

learning. Stimulating critical thinking among students must be one of the essential tasks of EFL teachers.

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